

A One Health Approach to Tackling Toxoplasmosis: *Current picture & future direction*

20 November 2025
Moredun Research Institute

The aim of this symposium is to bring together experts and stakeholders from a wide range of disciplines to discuss a One Health approach to tackling toxoplasmosis, a disease that intersects human, animal, and environmental health. We hope this symposium will provide a platform to discuss and assess the current epidemiological landscape of toxoplasmosis and to share ideas and innovations for detection and control, whilst also identifying critical knowledge gaps. We hope these discussions will help shape future research priorities and inform effective policy and intervention strategies to reduce the burden of *Toxoplasma gondii* across sectors.

Programme

9.00-9.30 Registration and Tea/Coffee

9.30-9.45 Welcome and Introduction

Dr Clare Hamilton

SESSION 1: MEDICAL / VETERINARY FOCUS

Chair: Professor Lee Innes, Moredun Research Institute

Lee is a Principal Scientist at the Moredun Research Institute where her career has focused on developing solutions to control diseases caused by protozoan parasites of livestock. She combines this with her role as Director of Communications where she has established collaborations with artists, film makers and podcasters to increase the reach and accessibility of Moredun's work. Lee was awarded an MBE in the New Years Honours in 2015 for services to scientific research and science communication,

and also holds Honorary Professorships at Heriot Watt University, University of Edinburgh and University of Glasgow. Lee was elected as a Fellow of the Royal Society of Edinburgh in 2017 and an Associate of the Royal Agricultural Societies in 2019. More recently, Lee successfully negotiated with the NHS and SRUC to set up testing of Covid samples during the pandemic to support the NHS and this was the first veterinary facility to do so showing the power of a One Health approach.

9.45-10.10

Human toxoplasmosis overview, and impact in Scotland

Dr Sally Mavin, Scottish Toxoplasma Reference Laboratory, Raigmore Hospital, Inverness

Dr Sally Mavin has been Director of the Scottish Toxoplasma Reference Laboratory (STRL), based at Raigmore Hospital in Inverness, since February 2020 and has worked on the laboratory diagnosis of toxoplasmosis as a clinical scientist for more than 20 years. The reference laboratory receives samples from patients from all over Scotland for confirmatory testing, offers scientific and clinical advice to healthcare staff from throughout Scotland and works closely

with colleagues in Public Health Scotland to collate and improve epidemiological information on toxoplasmosis.

Sally is a member of the UKNEQAS toxoplasma scientific advisory Group and has recently been working closely with colleagues at the Moredun Research Institute to improve the *T. gondii* cell culture system within the reference laboratory and further develop testing methods.

10.10-10.25

Incidence, diagnosis and impact of toxoplasmosis in England and Wales

Dr Stephen Hadfield, Toxoplasma Reference Unit, Public Health Wales, Swansea

Stephen Hadfield is a Consultant Clinical Scientist and Acting Head of the Toxoplasma Reference Unit for England and Wales. After gaining a Microbiology BSc (hons.) at Cardiff University and Virology MSc at Imperial College, London, he completed a PhD at the University of Southampton focused on quantitation of hepatitis C virus. He remained in Southampton to introduce molecular epidemiological methods for investigation of bacterial infections until joining Public Health Wales in 2002. He initially

worked at the national Cryptosporidium Reference Unit, developing molecular methods for detection and epidemiology of *Cryptosporidium* spp. Since 2014, he has worked at the national Toxoplasma Reference Unit which provides diagnostic and clinical advice services to support patient care throughout England and Wales, and also the Republic of Ireland. His research interests include development of methods for serodiagnosis, molecular detection and epidemiology of *Toxoplasma gondii*.

10.25-10.50 *Veterinary impact of toxoplasmosis*

Dr Andrew Robinson, SRUC

Andrew Robinson qualified from Glasgow Vet School in 1999 (having done an intercalated degree with a BSc in genetics in 1997) and worked in mixed practice for over 20 years. Two years ago, he joined SRUC Vet Services working out of St Boswells as a Veterinary Investigation Officer and combines this part-time role with a

part-time role working as a small animal vet in first opinion practice. Andrew has a particular interest in helping farmers maximise the efficiency and output of their sheep flocks. Outside of work he is trying to breed a thoroughbred fast enough to win a race.

10.50-11.05 *Vaccination as a control strategy for ovine abortion*

Sara Robson-Ingham, MSD

Sara Robson-Ingham is a Regional Veterinary Adviser (Ruminants) for MSD Animal Health, having previously spent several years working

as farm vet in a predominantly beef and sheep practice in County Durham.

11.05-11.25 **Tea/Coffee break**

SESSION 2: ENVIRONMENT / TRANSMISSION / RESEARCH FOCUS

Chair: Professor Fiona Henriquez, University of Strathclyde

Fiona gained her PhD in molecular parasitology, with the characterisation of dense granule proteins in the obligate parasite *Toxoplasma gondii*. She has continued in this area with a focus on host-pathogen interactions and parasite modulation of the host environment and immune response. Fascinated by toxoplasmosis in the eye, she began to work on the opportunistic pathogen, *Acanthamoeba* and the infection *Acanthamoeba* keratitis (AK). Her research focuses on the development of new

treatments and prevention measures for AK, and understanding the host-pathogen interactions, focusing on innate immune cells. Fiona's research contributes to the 'One Health' agenda and addresses several UN SDGs through interdisciplinary and cross-sector collaborators. She has gained experience and knowledge of the decision-making processes and communication channels in health economies, stakeholder mapping, drug development and environment disinfection.

11.25-11.50 **ONLINE: One Health approach to Toxoplasma gondii source attribution - TOXOSOURCES**

Professor Pikka Jokelainen, Statens Serum Institut, Denmark

Dr Pikka Jokelainen (DVM, MPG, PhD, Adj. prof.) is Head of Function for Infectious Disease Preparedness and One Health at Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark. Dr. Jokelainen has published over 130 scientific articles, mainly in the areas of One Health, zoonoses, infectious disease preparedness, and science-policy interfaces. They hold several leading roles in large European One Health and

preparedness initiatives, including coordinating EU-HIP consortium that supports countries to improve IT-systems towards interoperability, EU-WISH Joint Action on wastewater-based surveillance, as well as OH4Surveillance consortium that strengthens integrated One Health surveillance approaches for zoonotic pathogens. In 2020-2022, they coordinated One Health EJP TOXOSOURCES project.

11.50-12.15 *Genotyping of Toxoplasma gondii - Why, how and what typing results can be expected in the European context?*

Dr Gereon Schares, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Germany

Dr Gereon R.M. Schares is Scientific Director at the Friedrich Loeffler Institute, Federal Research Institute for Animal Health, Institute of Epidemiology, and Head of the German National Reference Laboratories for Echinococcosis, Toxoplasmosis, Dourine, and Surra.

Over the past decades, his laboratory has developed various methods for the detection and genetic characterization of zoonotic and veterinary parasites, as well as for identifying risk factors for their transmission to animals. Methods for the reliable detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in cat feces have been applied in large-scale, long-term epidemiological studies using cats as the definitive hosts of *T. gondii*. These studies revealed a seasonality in oocyst shedding. The development of diagnostic tools

for researching the epidemiology of other parasites also included the establishment of diagnostic procedures for the identification and characterization of veterinary parasites, e.g. *Neospora caninum*, an abortifacient in cattle, or *Besnoitia besnoiti*, a disease in cattle mechanically transmitted by insect vectors.

The isolation of viable parasites and their molecular typing methods were used to elucidate the global population structure of *T. gondii* and *N. caninum*. His laboratory identified highly polymorphic regions in the genomes of closely related *T. gondii* strains across Europe, and used a large number of strains from various parts of Europe to validate existing typing methods and establish a new Multilocus Sequence Typing method.

12.15-12.30 *Food and waterborne toxoplasmosis in Scotland*

Dr Clare Hamilton, Moredun Research Institute

Clare Hamilton is a senior research scientist working at the Moredun Research Institute on protozoan diseases of livestock. Clare first joined Moredun in 2000 as a research assistant in the protozoology group, before leaving to pursue a PhD on *Toxocara canis* at Trinity College Dublin. She remained in Dublin for 7 years working on liver fluke and teaching veterinary parasitology at University College Dublin. She

re-joined Moredun in 2013 where she led a collaborative research project with Ross University School of Veterinary Medicine in St. Kitts (West Indies) investigating the epidemiology and genetic diversity of *Toxoplasma gondii* in the Caribbean. Clare's current research interests are in ovine abortion, food and waterborne toxoplasmosis, and molecular epidemiology and transmission dynamics of protozoan parasites.

12.30-12.45 *In vitro tools for studying Toxoplasma gondii biology*

Dr David Smith, Moredun Research Institute

David Smith leads a cellular and molecular parasitology research group whose work covers a range of protozoan and helminth parasites. The main aim of David's group is to identify parasite molecules that underpin a successful infection and to use these as targets in the development of novel vaccines or therapeutics. A major component of the group's research over the past several years has been to develop physiologically relevant tissue culture models

derived from primary stem cells (i.e. organoids) for different mucosal tissues of cattle and sheep, including stomach, small and large intestine, upper and lower airway, liver and mammary. These models are now being applied to better understand host-parasites interactions and the parasite molecules for driving specific host responses (with a particular focus on immunomodulators), as well as to test novel mucosal vaccine adjuvants.

12.45-13.45 Lunch

13.45-14.45 Breakout discussion groups

1. What current tools do we have to tackle toxoplasmosis and are these effective?
2. What do we understand about the transmission routes of toxoplasmosis in the UK, and where are the knowledge gaps?
3. How aware are the public of toxoplasmosis and how can we improve this?

14.45-15.15 Reporting back and whole group discussion

15.15-15.30 Final summary and future plans